

Child's Age Estimation using Carpal Bones' Characterization

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ABSTRACT

Bone age estimation is a method of assigning a biological maturity level to an individual. The need of age estimation of the individual becomes important especially in clinical and forensic practices. Bone age estimation is used to estimate chronological age in condition where birth records are not available. It is also used in cases of unregistered child and juvenile court cases. In addition, bone age estimation is used to diagnose growth problem of the children. In this project, image segmentation of carpal bones using Dynamic Programming Gradient Inverse Coefficient of Variation (DPGICOV) is implemented and the characterization of the carpal bones based on morphological features is extracted to estimate the age of Asian male and female children under the age of 7 years old. Morphological features such as area, perimeter, shape, relative position of the carpal bones are extracted in this research. The results of this work show that based on carpal bones' characterization, the children's age can be estimated.

Keywords: bone age estimation; carpal bones; segmentation; feature extraction.

ABSTRAK

Anggaran umur tulang merupakan kaedah memberikan satu tahap kematangan biologi kepada individu. Keperluan anggaran umur individu menjadi semakin penting terutamanya dalam aplikasi klinikal serta bidang forensik. Anggaran umur tulang digunakan untuk menganggarkan umur kronologi dalam keadaan di mana rekod kelahiran tidak dapat didapati. Anggaran umur tulang juga digunakan dalam kes kanak-kanak yang tidak berdaftar dan kes mahkamah juvana kanak-kanak. Selain itu, anggaran umur tulang diperlukan untuk mendiagnosis masalah pertumbuhan kanak-kanak. Dalam kajian ini, segmentasi imej radiografi tulang karpal menggunakan teknik Pengaturcaraan Dinamik Pekali Variasi Gradien Songsang (PDPVGS) dilaksanakan dan pencirian tulang karpal berdasarkan ciri-ciri morfologi diekstrak bagi mendapatkan anggaran umur kanak-kanak lelaki dan perempuan Asia yang berumur di bawah 7 tahun. Ciri-ciri morfologi seperti luas, perimeter, bentuk, kedudukan relatif serta bilangan tulang karpal dapat diekstrak dalam kajian ini. Hasil kajian daripada kajian ini menunjukkan bahawa berdasarkan pencirian tulang karpal, umur kanak-kanak dapat dianggarkan.

Kata Kunci: anggaran umur tulang; tulang karpal; segmentasi; pengekstrakan ciri.

INTRODUCTION

Bone age assessment or skeletal maturity determination is a crucial part in diagnostic and therapeutic investigation involving endocrinological complications (development of bones and tissues), irregularity of children's growth and hereditary diseases (Poznanski et al. 1978). The assessment of bone age is done through a radiological examination

of the development of left hand which then is compared with the chronological age. Bone age is an indicator of bone maturity while chronological age is based on the date of birth of the individual. Difference between bone age and chronological age indicates that there are abnormalities in the individual's growth. Bone age assessment is accomplished by using some bones such as phalangeal, radius, ulna and carpal bones. Examination of the carpal bones to determine the age of the bone is widely used because it is much easier than other bones. Furthermore, carpal bones have minimal exposure to radiation and have various ossification centers for the assessment of bone maturation (Giordano et al. 2009). According to medical studies (Johnston & Jahina n.d.), carpal bones believed to be reliable in determining the bone age especially in children aged 0 to 6 years old. However, analysis of the carpal bones do not provide the right information to the age of 9-12 years. This is due to the overlapping of the carpal bones makes the analysis process becomes difficult. Carpal bones are vary in morphological features while undergoing the development process. For children under the age of 5-7 years, phalangeal analysis failed to get the accurate characteristics. This is due to soft tissue's boundaries deteriorated caused segmentation between epiphyseal and metaphyseal become difficult. In addition, the development of the epiphyseal for 6 phalangeal regions of interest are not parallel and not able detect the phalangeal region of interest correctly if the hands are rotated and not in the upright state. Phalangeal analysis is sensitive to bending of fingers during acquisition (Zhang et al. 2007). Bone age estimation is used to approximate the chronological age when there are no birth records available. In South Asia, 65% of births are not registered at the age of 5 years (Smith & Brownlees 2011). Carpal bones are chosen to estimate age of children instead of other bones as they have many ossification centres and their features changed in line with the children's age.

METHODOLOGY

In image processing, several steps are taken to estimate child's age using characterization of carpal bones. The image processing techniques consisting of image pre-processing, image segmentation and feature extraction are adopted in this study. X-ray image of hand is used in this study as shown in Figure 1 and the flow of this study is presented in Figure 2.

FIGURE 1 X-ray image of hand

Source <http://www.ipilab.org/BAAweb/>

FIGURE 2 Flowchart of the study

Referring to the Figure 2, the X-ray images of Asian male and female children were chosen as the input. Some enhancement is applied to the the original image. The background of the image is removed and the image's contrast is adjusted by manual thresholding depends on the image. In addition, the orientation of the image is also adjusted. The radiography image is then cropped to obtain carpal region of interest (CROI) only. The image enhancement is important for further analysis.

Then, the radiography images of carpal bones are segmented using Dynamic Programming Gradient Inverse Coefficient of Variation (DPGICOV) proposed by (Ray et al. 2012). This technique is used to find boundary of the

carpal bones perfectly. Gaussian filter is used for smoothing the CROI to facilitate the process of image segmentation. The basic of dynamic programming is depending on the generation of radial line. Virtual lines start at the centroid of carpal bones and went outward until reach the boundary of the carpal bones. A seed point is assigned for each carpal bones that represented as the centroid of the bones. The seed point is used to initialize the derivation of the bone boundary by using DPGICOV. Then it expanded and contracted in order to find the bone boundary properly.

Once all the carpal bones are segmented, feature extraction is performed. The morphological features such as area, perimeter, shape, relative position and number of bones are extracted from the radiography image of carpal bones. This step is essential for further analysis to map the growth profile of the children below 7 years old based on age and gender to determine the approximate their chronological age. Based on Figure 3, the centroid of the capitate is used as the reference point to extract the relative position which are angle and distance of the other bones. From the angle obtained, the carpal bones are divided into five zones.

FIGURE 3 Estimation of relative position of the carpal bones

From the data obtained, the growth profile is plotted based on each morphological features for both male and female children. The purpose for this step is to observe the development of the carpal bones and the children's growth. The development of carpal bones helps to determine the approximate age of the child. This is due to the area, perimeter, shape, relative position and number of the carpal bones vary according to age. After data profiling is done, age estimation is made to approximate the child's age based on the characterization of carpal bones.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the radiography images of hand for both male and female Asian children is processed in order to estimate their chronological age based on the characterization of the carpal bones. The images are enhanced to get better quality of image for the segmentation. The images then are segmented using DPGICOV to determine the boundary of each carpal bones. After that, morphological features are extracted from the carpal bones for further analysis.

Figure 4 shows the segmentation results for seven carpal bones in two situations which no bones overlapped and presence of bones overlapped (trapezium and trapezoid). This proves that the technique is reliable which it can find the boundary of the bones and even overlapping bones properly. The characterization of carpal bones based on morphological features is extracted from the segmented carpal bones. Area, perimeter, shape, relative position and number of carpal bones are acquired in this study. The shown results are based on the average value of each morphological features.

The ossification of carpal bones occur since newborn and developed year by year. From Table 1, it shows the range of number of bones by age for male and female children. The number of bones ossified are different between them. Female's bone is developed since newborn while male's bone is developed a year later that is at 1 years old. This show that female children mature faster compared to male children.

From the plotted graph shown in Figure 5, the number of bones increases as the year increases. Same goes with area and perimeter that shows increment when children's age increase as can be observed in Figure 6 and Figure 7. Furthermore, the shape of carpal bones also changes. Eccentricity is chosen to represent the shape of carpal bones. Based on Table 2 and Table 3, the range value of eccentricity is from 0 until 1. For each carpal bone, the closer the value to 0, the more circular the bone is. While the closer the value 1, the bone is more likely an ellipse. On the other

hand, the angle of the carpal bones are divided into five zones. There is a bone in each zone but in zone 5, there are two bones exist. In order to distinguish which are trapezium and trapezoid, range of angle for both bones are considered.

But, the graphs show some declination at some points. This is because in this study, the images used are not from the same individual but from different persons for each age. Usually, carpal bones will ossify in order. Capitate will be the first bone to ossify following by hamate, triquetral, lunate, scaphoid, trapezium and trapezoid. However, there are cases that the carpal bones not developed according to this order depends on the individual. This affect the results gained in this study. Moreover, the study is not based on continuous monitoring of the similar persons. So it gives variation to the results obtained.

FIGURE 4 Image segmentation of seven carpal bones

TABLE 1 Range of number of bones based on age

Age(year)	No. of bones	
	Male	Female
0		2
1	2	2 – 3
2	2 – 4	2 – 4
3	2 – 3	4 – 6
4	2 – 6	3 – 6
5	4 – 7	3 – 7
6	6 – 7	7
7	6 – 7	7

FIGURE 5 Graph of number of bones based on age (a)male (b)female

FIGURE 6 Graph of area of carpal bones based on age (a)male (b)female

FIGURE 7 Graph of perimeter of carpal bones based on age (a)male (b)female

TABLE 2 Eccentricity of carpal bones based on age (male)

Bone Age (Year)	Capitate	Hamate	Triquetral	Lunate	Scaphoid	Trapezium	Trapezoid
0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	0.5657	0.4948	-	-	-	-	-
2	0.6037	0.4245	0.4619	0.7069	-	-	-
3	0.6461	0.5280	-	-	-	-	-
4	0.7651	0.6280	0.6255	0.6255	0.6786	0.7070	-
5	0.7518	0.6594	0.6255	0.6002	0.6941	0.6231	0.5517
6	0.7834	0.6932	0.6529	0.5686	0.6914	0.6170	0.4555
7	0.6952	0.6887	0.5585	0.6508	0.6224	0.6054	0.4335

TABLE 3 Eccentricity of carpal bones based on age (male)

Bone Age (Year)	Capitate	Hamate	Triquetral	Lunate	Scaphoid	Trapezium	Trapezoid
0	0.4981	0.3924					
1	0.6189	0.5050	0.3700				
2	0.7271	0.5528	0.6071	0.4449			
3	0.7769	0.6376	0.6419	0.5737		0.6054	0.3290
4	0.7569	0.6170	0.5857	0.5344		0.4445	0.4198
5	0.7888	0.6699	0.6104	0.5585	0.5566	0.5252	0.5282
6	0.6694	0.6773	0.6813	0.6293	0.6268	0.5840	0.4127
7	0.7252	0.6128	0.6889	0.6580	0.6722	0.5326	0.4265

CONCLUSION

Carpal bones showed more changes in morphological features compared to phalangeal, ulna and radius bones in line with the age of children. The characterization of carpal bone from the bone segmentation helps in estimating the children’s age below 7 years old. Results also showed that the Asian children’s growth development can be differentiated based on gender.

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